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TITLE: In what aspects can different network analysis techniques help readers to understand the story differently: A social network analysis of the English translation of Chinese Classics 'Water Margin'

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- The total length of the dissertation (text and footnotes) is **11,897** words.

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In what aspects can different network analysis techniques help readers to interpret the story differently?

A SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS OF THE ENGLISH TRANSLATION OF CHINESE CLASSICS “WATER MARGIN”

Abstract

This paper aims to explore the possibilities and limitations of how different network analysis techniques could help readers understand the social network within the fictional world of *Water Margin*. Different methodologies are summarised from the review of four case studies. A comparative study will be implemented on those methodologies to select the optimal method for conducting the social network analysis. The optimal method will subsequently be utilised to conduct different types of social network analysis.

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1. Introduction

This paper describes the social network analysis conducted by its author. The writing analysed here is a piece of Chinese classical literature, *Water Margin*, written by Shi Nai'an in the mid-14th Century. This paper is a methodological essay describing the processes of determining the optimal procedures of conducting a social network analysis on the novel named *Water Margin*. The outputs of this analysis are subsequently inspected manually, and further research is conducted to explore how the quantifiable analytical methods aid us in understanding the textual data and relational dynamics between the characters.

1.1 Definition of Social Network Analysis

As defined in Barnes' writing, social networks represent the social-relationship concept of social scientists or the general public and systematically present the relationship model by using graphs, with actors, relationships, and linkages (Barnes, cited in Chen & et al., 2021). Approaching the notion of social network as a research methodology, Wasserman and Faust proposed to define it as a research method in sociology, mainly entailing the action of searching for potential social network structure from the interaction model between the social actors, relationships, and linkages (Wasserman & Faust, 1994).

In this case study, the novel's characters pose as the nodes in a social network. As the basic unit of a social network, a node represents an individual or an organisation. Nodes comprise the body of the social network, represented as individual points on the map of the social network. The edges represent a relationship between nodes. *Edges* are defined as the linkages among characters of message exchange (Chen & et al., 2021), name mentioning, affiliation, conversations, co-occurrence, and other interactions (Labatut & Bost, 2020). Relationships between the nodes could be divided into directed or undirected. A directed network often represent a non-reciprocal relationship. Vice versa, an undirected network represents a reciprocal relationship. Hence, a character network is a graph extracted from the narrative, in which nodes represent characters and edges correspond to interactions between characters.

1.2 Introduction of the Text

The focal object of our social network analysis is the text *Water Margin*, a Chinese classical literature written by Shi Nai'an. The novel was written in the mid-14th Century,

and its widespread success has lasted for centuries. Until after the Chinese Cultural Revolution, *Water Margin* had been officially acknowledged as one of the four most outstanding pieces of Chinese classical literature, alongside three other Chinese classics, namely the Journey to the West, Dream of the Red Chamber and Romance of the Three Kingdoms (Samuels, 2018). The authorship of the novel remains a subject of discussion for historians, many of whom have argued that *Water Margin* was co-written by Shi Nai'an and his disciple, Luo Guanzhong, the author of Romance of the Three Kingdoms (DayDayNews, 2019).

Water Margin is a story about how one hundred and eight rebels congregated and formed an alliance known as the Liangshan Marsh. They swore to fight against the social injustice enforced by the corrupted officials from the Imperial Court. The novel consists of one hundred chapters, and these chapters are grouped into three sections. The first section, unfolding from chapter one to chapter forty, depicts the personal stories of selected rebels. These stories are independent yet interconnected. The second section runs from chapter forty-one to chapter eighty, and it narrates the congregation of rebels and the construction of the Liangshan Marsh under the lead of Song Jiang, the protagonist. Additionally, this second section tells the war stories of the Liangshan Marsh fighting against the corrupted bureaucrats and underground power. The third section, lasting from chapter eighty-one to chapter one hundred, highlights the defeats in war and the terrible loss of comrades of the Liangshan Marsh, which followed the amnesty approval from the Imperial Court.

This social network analysis is not conducted on the original version of the novel written in Vernacular Chinese but instead analyses the English translation of *Water Margin* completed by Sidney Shapiro. When Shapiro was about to finish his translation work on *Water Margin*, he was compelled under the socio-political environment of his

time to change the alternative name of the novel from 'Heroes of the Marsh' to 'Outlaws of the Marsh' (Abarams, 1985). During the Chinese Cultural Revolution, the radical political alliance believed that the acts of the revolutionists who later sought amnesty (including the actions of Song Jiang, the protagonist) were cowardly, and Chinese proletariats should not submit to the imperialist's ideology. The radical politicians saw the Party's Chairmans Zhou Enlai and Deng Xiaoping represented in the characters of the novel's surrenderers, Song Jiang and Wu Yong. Deng and Zhou undermined the cause of the Cultural Revolution and Mao's legitimacy to rule China. In the novel, Song Jiang and Wu Yong undermined the former rebel leader Chao Gai's legitimacy to lead the Liangshan Marsh and challenged Chao's tactics in achieving a corruption-free state (Fitzgerald, 1986, p366). Under the perceived parallel between the novel's characters and actual political figures at the time, Shapiro was forced to label the characters as 'outlaws' and not as the 'bandit-heroes' Shi originally depicted them to be.

1.3 Structuring the Research Paper

The research paper is separated into five parts, namely the literature review, case study review, research methodology, discussion of findings, and conclusion. The research limitations and future research direction are provided after this paper concludes.

The author plans to discuss the definition of network analysis in the digital humanities field within the literature review section. The ways in which scholars use social network analysis as a digital humanities tool in studying different information are explored in this section. Subsequently, the nature of the interactions in the world of *Water Margin*

is depicted and identified. In the case study review, the author aims to understand the different methods scholars used to achieve character identification, character extraction, relationship extraction, network visualisation and node clustering. A brief summary of these methods is provided, the methods mentioned in the case studies will be selected, followed by pinpointing the general direction and methodology used to conduct this social network analysis. In the methodology section, the procedures in conducting social network analysis on novels will be illustrated step-by-step. After the procedure illustration, the outputs derived from social network analysis procedures will be compared using different computational methods. The outputs will subsequently be discussed in the discussion section.

2. Literature Review:

Humanities scholars have widely adopted social network analysis theories and methodologies in their respective academic fields. Moretti applied social networks theory to the plot analysis of texts and found the key characters through macro social network and character-centred social network (Moretti, 2011). Jackson applied social network analysis on the database known as 'People of Medieval Scotland' and identified additional roles played by Duncan II, the Earl of Fife. Jackson also applied the social network density model to identify opinion leaders in medieval Scotland based on the database (Jackson, 2017). Padgett and Ansell applied social network analysis on the political parties and elites networks that underlaid the birth of the Renaissance State in Florence. In their study, the degree of centrality of Cosimo de' Medici was measured, uncovering that Cosimo had many vocations and connections, and he was a member of both elite marriage networks and numerous business partnerships. These varied memberships and positions allowed him to be a banker

who influenced Florence's economy and politics (Padgett & Ansell, 1993). Moretti pushed this area of research even further by identifying the relationships between social connections and culture.

Moretti's research on network theory offers distinct insights. His study offers a methodological comparison between conducting the social network analysis of a Chinese classic novel *Dream of Red Chamber* and determining the relationship status between the novel's characters. Moretti argues that the *guanxi* (Chinese word for relationships) in *Dream of the Red Chamber* are complex, and they do not necessarily signify power (Moretti, 2011), unlike suggested in Padgett and Ansell's analysis of the social network of Cosimo de' Medici (Padgett & Ansell, 1993). Moretti used Gold, Guthrie and Wank's (2009) framework of *guanxi* to study the Chinese-style relationships between characters. Gold, Guthrie et al. (2009) explained that the relationships among Chinese people, and the characters authentically representing them in literature, entail high levels of complexity. *Guanxi* involves feelings of *ganqing* (sentiment), *renqing* (human feelings), *mianzi* (honour) and *bao* (reciprocity) (Gold et al., 2009).

Having applied Gold, Guthrie and Wank's framework of *guanxi*, Moretti finds that relations in the novel constructed a world that is neither individual nor society-based but relation-based. These relations are not a given but pose as an artefact. The lexicon of *guanxi* includes but is not limited to the words and actions such as 'manufacturing obligation', 'chain of transaction', 'indebtedness', and 'consciously producing connections'. Moretti took Jia Baoyu, the protagonist in the novel, as an example to illustrate his theory. Jia is a male child born with a good omen from a Chinese noble family, and he was expected to contribute to his family by bringing a divine blessing. However, in reality, the interactions Jia had in the novel involved constantly being

summoned by relatives, mitigating relations between the clans, running errands for his family, and being kept under the supervision of all members of the high society of Chinese noble clans. His duty constrains Jia's freedom towards the relation-based society he is part of (Moretti, 2011). Moretti concluded that the different role assumed by the protagonist results from a different set of narrative relations. To gain a richer image of the social network in *Dream of Red Chamber*, Moretti believes an enormous amount of empirical data must be first assembled (Moretti, 2011).

Moretti's research makes one reader acknowledge that in order to study the relationship between characters, researchers must understand the context within which these relationships are based. For *Water Margin*, Song believes readers should understand '*Jianghu*' (Rivers and Lakes) in addition to Gold, Guthrie and Wank's concept on *guanxi* (Song, 2019). According to Song, the term '*Jianghu*' refers to an imagined spatial arena in Chinese literature and culture that is parallel to, or sometimes in a tangential relationship with, the mainstream society inhabited by men. This term originates from the geographical imagination of water as a dangerous and remote substance. Song borrowed French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu's definition of a 'field', who had defined *Jianghu* as a 'field' that is constructed by its various norms, taboos, jargon, and codes of behaviour. The masculine codes, such as 'en' (grace, favour), 'yi' (righteousness), and 'chou' (vengeance), constitute its members' major sources of social capital.

In *Jianghu*, members are not their own masters but are rather manipulated by the rules and codes that prevail in those 'fields' (Song, 2019). *Jianghu* is an imagined yet institutionalised community in *Water Margin*. It prescribes a whole set of brotherhood-centred moral and behavioural codes cherished as sacrosanct by the *Jianghu* members. In this imagined community, *Jianghu* members call each other brothers,

making no distinction between genders, family origins and social classes. However, the romantic and egalitarian nature of the brotherhood is merely an illusion. As represented in *Water Margin*, the relationship amongst the outlaws inevitably become hierarchical as the stronghold expands and the establishment of law and order ensues. Taking the protagonist Song Jiang as an example: before the death of Song Jiang, he poisoned his most loyal *Jianghu* brother, Li Kui, to protect the chivalry of the Liangshan Marsh. However, it is apparent that Song Jiang was insecure and took advantage of the oblivious Li Kui to protect his definition of 'righteousness' of this outlaw establishment. Most importantly of all, he acted to protect his personal reputation within the *Jianghu*.

The *Jianghu* behaviour codes in *Water Margin* guide its followers to despise the governors' behaviour of 'going through the backdoor' through *guanxi* to achieve political/financial gains. However, some members of the Liangshan Marsh have violated those moral codes by their unlawful conduct. Take Lin Chong as an example. When he was sentenced to imprisonment, informants tipped him that if bribery was given to the prison wardens, the wardens would treat the prisoner with due respect. Although he knew his conduct would not be accepted in the *Jianghu* community, Lin Chong bribed the wardens. If the similarity of Song Jiang and Lin Chong were to be compared, it is apparent that there are Marsh members who benefited from the *Jianghu* moral codes, and there are Marsh members who were restricted/oppresed by the *Jianghu* moral codes. However, as Moretti has stated, an enormous dataset of empirical data is needed to gain a richer image of characters' roles and relationships (Moretti, 2011).

In the following part of the essay, the author will conduct four comparative case studies on the researchers implementing social network analyses on the literature. The first

goal for the following section is to find a feasible method to quantify characters' interactions accurately and construct the social network. The second goal is to find the method for presenting qualitative information of characters through network analysis and depict a richer image of characters within their social network.

3. Case study Review

In this section of the paper, the author will illustrate four case studies on how numerous scholars attempted to reflect fictional character's relationships by conducting social network analysis on novels. These four case studies are, *Network analysis of Dream of Red Chamber*, *Network analysis of Romance of The Three Kingdoms*, *Network Analysis of Game of Thrones: A Song of Ice and Fire*, *Literary Character Networks* by Jennifer Isasi. After reading these four case study reviews, readers will gain a deeper understanding of the logic behind how each social network is made, and the most important of all, how these four conductors attempt to maximise the relationship recalls precision. Unfortunately, the author has not obtained the rights to share the visualisations for these four network analysis case studies. However, the links for these case studies will be given in the bibliography for readers who wish to gain full comprehension.

3.1 Social Network Analysis of Dream of Red Chamber

Similar to the author of this paper, Chen and his fellow researchers share the same ambition to construct a social network visualisation on Chinese Classics that depicts the actual relationship between relationships.

The first step in conducting a social network analysis is to identify characters within the novel. Chen and his fellow researchers utilised the Stanford NER algorithm to

extract the list of important characters, using linear chain Conditional Random Field (CRF) models, followed by a manual inspection to expurgate the false positives. (Chen et.al, 2019, p.802) After merging the synonyms of characters names, they have obtained the total occurrence of all characters and the characters' occurrence ranked from highest to lowest, selected top 100 occurrence characters to filter the 'noise'. According to Labatut and Bost, certain network analysers remove characters deemed not frequently enough, considering those low occurrence characters as noise. (Labatut & Bost, 2020, p.15)

The next step following character extractions is to identify the relationship between characters. Chen and his fellow researchers adopted character pairing patterns similarity as their relationship measurement units in this case study. In this analysis step, it is vital to consider the appropriate size the text should be subdivided to. For Chen's team, they vectorised all the occurrences of the top 100 frequently appeared characters, and cosine measure of the weight between each character interaction pattern:

$$w_{i,j} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{120} a_k^i a_k^j}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^{120} (a_k^i)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^{120} (a_k^j)^2}}$$

The similarity score of characters activity patterns will later be converted into distance applying the following formula:

$$d_{i,j} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\max(t, w_{i,j})} - 1},$$

As a result, Chen's team has adopted an unconventional way of extracting character relationships by measuring interaction patterns. Nevertheless, this unconventional

method will require an additional step to convert the weight into the distance. The frequency of character co-occurrences in each chapter validates the social distance between every pair of characters. Chen and his fellow researchers further continued their research into constructing minimum span clustering (MSC) to identify how different patterns of character relationship cluster to a similar pattern of relationship (Chen et al., 2019, p.801).

3.2 Social Network Analysis of Romance of The Three Kingdoms

Similar to the previous case study, Manolidis attempted to conduct a social network analysis of another great Chinese Classics, *Romance of The Three Kingdoms*. (Manolidis, 2019) However, unlike the unique clustering method designed by Chen's research team, Manolidis took a relatively passive approach in identifying the clusters between characters compare to Chen's method. Manolidis's character clusters rely on the built-in clustering functions provided by Gephi.

The original text *Romance of The Three Kingdoms* has more than one thousand characters vary from warlords to commoners, for the character extraction process. Manolidis believes such an extensive network would become unreadable as it is too 'noisy' (Labatut & Bost, 2020, p.15), and it does not contribute to a higher character network precision. Henceforth, Manolidis has manually made a list of high occurrence characters and the characters he likes. As a result, he generated a list of 70 characters.

According to Labatut & Bost's survey on social network analysis of fictional characters, Labatut and Bost have summarised the common narrative units defined by other network analysis conductors. In short, the main difference between different narrative units is their size. Some conductors like Rochat & Kaplan chose to use 'page' as the narrative unit (Rochat & Kaplan, 2014), or others like Chen would like to use 'chapters' as the narrative unit. (Chen et.al, 2019, p802) Small narrative units could vary from sentences (Lee & Yeung, 2012) to paragraphs

(Elsner, 2012, p.636). For this case study, Manolidis used Beveridge & Shan's method in relationship extraction, in which the narrative unit has shrunk into a finer narrative unit of "15 words combination" (Manolidis, 2020). If multiple characters' names co-occurred in any 15 words combinations, that would count as one or more interactions between characters. (Beveridge & Shan, 2016, p.19) With all 15 words combinations, this method will certainly extract a higher frequency than splitting the text into sentences or paragraphs narrative units. However, suppose the 15 words combination method has been applied consistently to the text. In that case, we can assume the network scale will remain authentic even the interaction frequencies are higher than usual.

Manolidis took a different approach in analysing the centrality of characters' social networks. *Romance of The Three Kingdoms* consists of 120 chapters. Manolidis separated these 120 chapters into four phases of the story, thirty chapters each phase. In each phase, Manolidis visualised the characters' social network and plot out his calculation on the top centrality degrees, betweenness centrality and eigenvector centrality. As a result of the centrality analysis, Manolidis has used them to validate his perceptions on the most influential warlord and other warlords who have powerful friends over the evolution of four phases (Manolidis, 2019).

3.3 Social Network Analysis of Game of Thrones: A Song of Ice and fire

This case study took a similar approach as Manolidis' social network analysis. The fantasy fiction *Game of Thrones* is a popular fantasy drama television series. The TV series is a television adaptation of the fantasy novel series *A Song of Ice and Fire*. The author declares that this social network analysis will not cover visual character extraction or visual narratives in the *Game of Thrones* TV series. This analysis focuses on the textual extraction of fictional characters and their relationship in the novel *A*

Song of Ice and Fire. The conductor of this social network analysis is Andrew Beveridge.

In their report, they did not mention how the characters' names were extracted from the novels. However, let us inspect the source files from Beveridge's Github repository. From the list of nodes, we could deduce that Beveridge took a similar approach in the character extraction process as Manolidis. Both social network analyses involved creating a list by extracting characters' names from external resources (Beveridge & Hunger, 2017). On the other hand, Beveridge did not filter the list of characters like Manolidis did. It is evident that Beveridge has moved the network filtering process to the subsequent relationship extraction process.

As the author mentioned from Manolidis' case study, Beveridge and Shan used the "15 words combinations" method to identify the relationship between every character. (Beveridge & Shan, 2017, p.19) It is interesting to see almost 800 nodes created for the social network, but not all nodes are shown in their visualisations. Therefore, a deduction is made that the 'noise' has been reduced to 107 vertices during the interaction extraction process. (Beveridge & Shan, 2017, p.18)

Beveridge and Shan applied the Louvain community detection algorithm to the Game of Thrones social network. According to the research fellows Blondel, Guillaume, Lambiotte and Lefebvre from Louvain University, the modularity of large networks and its community detection accuracy could be optimized dramatically by applying the Louvain community detection algorithm. (Blondel et al., 2008) The Louvain community detection algorithm has been adapted as the main modularity algorithm for Gephi. (Wang, 2020) Hence, Beveridge and Shan used the same methodology clustering characters as Manolidis.

Beveridge took a further step in conducting centrality analysis compared to Manolidis. Apart from the centrality degrees, betweenness degrees and eigenvector centralities, Beveridge also measured the weighted degree, page rank and closeness centralities. From these six centralities measurements, Beveridge has gained a more robust comprehension in power and influence within characters.

3.4 Social Network Analysis of Spanish Literary Character Networks

This case study will focus on Isasi's report on her research "Possibilities for the Digital Data Mining for the analysis of the Literary characters in the Spanish Novel: The Case of Galdós' National Episodes". The main goal of Isasi's project is to create a pipeline for extracting and analysing character networks in novels written in Spanish. The corpus she has for this project is 46 Spanish novels, also a list containing 4400 characters occurred in those 46 novels with metadata indicating all characters' resolved names, token names, social class, historical or fictional, gender. (Isasi, 2017) The author believes this case study stands in a unique position as we compared it to many existing projects of novel network analysis because it involves analysing and visualising qualitative information of characters.

As mentioned before, Isasi has constructed a list of 4400 characters as part of her corpus for this project. Isasi did not mention how those characters' names were extracted from the 46 novels in this report. Therefore, it is assumable that Isasi has taken a similar approach as Manolidis and Beveridge in characters extraction. However, Isasi has taken a further step in assigning additional qualitative features to each character (Isasi, 2017). As a result, Isasi could visualise the characters' clusters not based on quantitative measurement offered by Gephi's modularity algorithm but based on qualitative conditions of each character.

In terms of character relationship extraction, Isasi has controlled the narrative unit into one paragraph. Isasi counted the co-occurrence of characters' names for each relationship between characters in the same chapter. There is no need for characters to interact in any exact plotline (Isasi, 2017). Due to the unavailability of Isasi's project source codes, the author could not access if Isasi has also counted the weight of each relationship in each chapter, in other words, the frequencies of each relationship.

For visualisation, Isasi has constructed 46 networks from 46 novels. We could see that each node (character) is more likely to be situated with other nodes who share a similar social class (Isasi, 2017). In Isasi's preliminary study on the social class distribution in individual novels, she found out that these Spanish novels often depict the relationships from two social groups of characters, the upper class and military (Isasi, 2017). The prevalent occurrences of these two social groups distributions in these Spanish novels could use it as an emphasis point in studying the genre conventions of Spanish novels.

From Isasi's social network analysis report, the author sees a new possibility in conducting social network analysis with qualitative metadata as support. A new way in studying novels' genre conventions, and more importantly, to uncover the hidden humanistic features that shape the culture and society novels represented.

3.5 Case study summaries and my project direction

From the four case studies above, we have identified the crucial steps in conducting social network analysis. Which are character extraction, relationship extraction, character clustering and data visualisation (Labatut & Bost, 2020). Every case study has its unique methodology in identifying characters' relationships.

From Chen's network analysis of *Dream of Red Chamber*, they used a rule-based Stanford NER algorithm to extract characters' names from the text, construct relationship network by measuring character's relationship similarities scores, and they designed their clustering method by implementing MSC techniques (Chen & et al., 2019).

Arguably, Manolidis' network analysis of *Romance of The Three Kingdoms* was conducted with almost the same methodology as Beveridge's *Network of Thrones* project. Both case studies take the same approach in manually create a list of characters for the character extraction process. Both used the '15 words combinations' method to extract the relationship between characters, both used Gephi's built-in modularity algorithm for character clustering, and both conducted centrality analysis (Manolidis, 2020) However, Beveridge analysed conducted three additional centrality measures than Manolidis (Beveridge & Shan, 2017).

The corpus of Isasi's social network analysis consists of a list of 4400 characters and 46 novels. The unique feature of Isasi's network is that each character has been assigned metadata that encode their social class, gender, and other qualitative information (Isasi, 2017).

To find the social network analysis methodology for the social network analysis on *Water Margin*, the author has decided to conduct the network analysis with the methodologies implemented in the case studies.

1. The manual creation method of the character list has been adopted for my character extraction, in which it will be used for my NER model training.

2. For relationship extraction, the author has decided to compare the entity recognition precision on the '15 words combination' method, 'small narrative unit' method and 'large narrative unit' method.
3. Once the precision in relationship extraction is optimal, the author will visualise the network through Gephi and have all nodes clustered through Gephi's modularity algorithm.
4. The final output of the network will be used to analyse the character's centralities.
5. In the last stage of the network analysis, the author will use Stanford's Palladio as the network visualisation tool. Focus on visualising the qualitative data of characters in a geospatial network.

4. Methodology

In this section of the paper, the author aims to illustrate to readers the methods author used for character extraction, interaction extraction, and data visualisation in the social network analysis on *Water Margin*. For data extraction, the author first intended to manually extract the list of characters for training the NER model. However, the author later discovered it was not necessary to train the NER model to extract character interactions, the list of character names is the only thing needed for extracting interactions. After the characters are extracted, the list of characters will be used to identify character's undirected interactions in three methods, which are Isasi's one co-occurrence between a pair of characters per chapter (Isasi, 2017), '15 words

combinations' from Beveridge and Shan (Beveridge & Shan, 2017), 'two-paragraphs interaction extraction' from Elsner. (Elsner, 2012)

4.1 Character extraction

The author has decided to use Spacy, the natural language processing (NLP) package, to train the named entity recognition (NER) model for character extraction. However, before the training of the NER model, Spacy requires a list of character names documented in JSON format. This character names list could be obtained either automatically or manually. The model will be used to obtain the total occurrence of all characters across each chapter in the novel once the model is trained.

Spacy relies on their built-in English language model to tokenise sentences and identify the potential names of either organisation or person within the text for the automatic process. Users could enhance NER accuracy by choosing Spacy's large English language model. However, the text this project works on is an English translation of Chinese text. There are many 'name' words that require manual inspection. Take the protagonist Song Jiang as an example, Song Jiang can be abbreviated to Song, and it clashes with the name of the dynasty in the story that took place, the Song Dynasty. As a result, the automatic name extraction process through NER will strongly negatively impact the accuracy of the names extracted in text. Henceforth, the author proposes to use the alternative manual process to obtain character names.

The manual character extraction process could also implement automatically or manually. In Mattingly's experiment with building the NER model for the Harry Potter novel, Mattingly used the Python package BeautifulSoup to extract Harry Potter

character names on the Harry Potter Wikipedia page (Mattingly, 2020). However, Mattingly's method was not adopted in this research. This is because some of the character names on the Wikipedia page *Water Margin*¹ do not match our text. Two hypotheses could explain this phenomenon. First hypothesis: *Water Margin* Wikipedia page editors used the Chinese Pinyin pronunciation method to romanise the Chinese characters. For instance, the romanisation of a character named 鲁智深 (lǔ zhì shēn) will be romanised to Lu Zhishen. The romanised character names in the Wikipedia page do not match the characters' romanised names translated by Sidney Shapiro. Second hypothesis: the Wikipedia page editors used the romanised character names from another version of the English translation of *Water Margin, All Men Are Brothers* translated by Pearl Buck. As some of the character names on the Wikipedia page did not match with Shapiro's version of the text translation, the author took the liberty to extract character names manually from the Wikipedia page and alter the incorrect romanised names by inspection. As a result of the manual extraction and alteration after inspection, the author has extracted a list of three hundred- and twenty-three-character names and documented it in JSON format. Spacy's NER model training commenced once the character file has been documented. Once the NER model is trained, the model is then applied to the Python codes to extract all character names within each chapter. As a result, a JSON file containing the complete character occurrence information is created.

¹ Wikipedia, (2021) '*Wikipedia: List of Water Margin characters*', available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Water_Margin_characters

4.2.1 Interaction identification: One occurrence between two characters per chapter

Subsequently, to calculate the co-occurrences between *Water Margin* characters, the author has written a Javascript code to calculate Isasi's co-occurrence measurement. Although the Javascript code could accurately calculate the times of co-occurrence across a hundred chapters, the drawback of this method is that it takes a very long time to input the character names to generate the co-occurrence queries. Due to the impracticality of this method, the author has only calculated the co-occurrences between 36 characters (the 36 Heavenly Spirits) to save time. Hence, a total of 630 queries made manually as character relationship are undirected.

The visualisation of this dataset does not show any strong character ties, the author believes it is caused by Isasi's definition of co-occurrence is restrictive as it ignores the repetition of character names in each character, interactions between a pair of characters calculate only once. The visualisation of this method will be further discussed in the observation section. The author will adopt Beveridge & Shan 'fifteen words combination' methodology to calculate interactions in the next method.

4.2.2 Interaction identification: fifteen words combinations

Manolidis and Beveridge implemented the 'fifteen words combinations' co-occurrence calculation. Their case studies revealed that this method identified character interactions when more than two names appeared within any fifteen words combinations (Beveridge & Shan, 2017). Henceforth, two characters within fifteen words will make one co-occurrence, three characters make three co-occurrences, four characters make six co-occurrences, five characters make ten co-occurrences.

Compared to Isasi's interaction identification methodology, this methodology offers higher precision in identifying interactions as it is not as restrictive as Isasi's method. The increase of precision comes from two sides. On the one hand, the narrative unit is minimised from Isasi's one chapter to any fifteen words. Therefore, any fifteen words with multiple characters co-occurred throughout any chapter, it would consider as one or more interactions. Fifteen words are more likely to signify the proximity between characters than generally identifying a singular interaction between characters in one chapter. On the other hand, the high frequency of interactions enables us to represent how frequently the author puts two characters in proximity, which can later be added as the weight of edges.

Additionally, the author believes the number of words combinations should be compared and validated. In other words, both Manolidis and Beveridge believe fifteen words combinations were the optimal amount of word combinations to process their corpus, but will it also fit the *Water Margin* text corpus? What if Shapiro's translated the text in concise writing that it takes less than fifteen words to define a co-occurrence. Hence, to answer this question, the author has conducted this method in ten words combinations and fifteen words combinations. By conducting this process, the author could compare how many nodes and edges each combination identifies. As a result, 272 nodes and 1578 edges are identified in the ten words combinations, 289 nodes and 2141 edges are identified in the fifteen words combinations. This result assumes that the character relationship in our text translation could work fine with the fifteen words combinations introduced by Beveridge. The author's concern on Shapiro simplified translation does not negatively impact the relationship identification accuracy.

4.2.3 Interaction identification: Two paragraphs

Elsner implemented the 'two-paragraphs' co-occurrence identification method in his study of *Pride and Prejudice* (Elsner, 2012). This method identifies character co-occurrences within two paragraphs. This method identifies character co-occurrence similarly to the fifteen words combinations. Within each narrative unit (two paragraphs), two characters make one co-occurrence, three make three co-occurrences, four make six co-occurrences. The main difference between this method is that this method will not be restricted to the word counts as the other method was restricted to the word limit of fifteen.

Apart from the similarity on how co-occurrences are calculated between the two-paragraphs method and fifteen words combination method, the author also shares the same previous concern on the paragraph(s) as the narrative unit method. The author had to decide whether should one paragraph or two paragraphs as a narrative unit. The prominent advantage of choosing one paragraph as a narrative unit is precision. The advantage of high semantic precision is given because generally, in writing, each paragraph provides a "central meaning", sentences are then consecutively added to the paragraph to bring colours to the central meaning. However, the author hypothesises that this advantage of high semantic precision is a drawback in identifying co-occurrence if one paragraph focuses on one character. To validate this hypothesis, the author has compared nodes and edges identification between the one paragraph method and the two-paragraphs methods. The result shows 300 nodes and 5234 edges are identified in the one paragraph method, 307 nodes and 6017 edges are identified in the two-paragraphs method. Hence, it is assumable that the two-paragraphs method can identify seven characters more and 783 edges more than the one paragraph method.

It is also essential to consider the consequences the two-paragraphs method brings. The other main reason why the author has not adopted Isasi's method is that Isasi's calculation connotes 'one chapter has only once scene' (Isasi, 2017). So, when characters co-occurred in one chapter and only once per chapter, Isasi disregarded the possibility that one chapter could have multiples scenes. For instance, if our narrative unit for the two-paragraphs method unfortunately lied within two scenes, paragraph one depicts scene A and paragraph two depicts scene B. There is a possibility our algorithm will draw up a lot of non-existent character relationships with their misassigned co-occurrences. On the other side of the coin, the seven additional nodes identified in the two-paragraphs method signifies that there are seven characters that could not be identified without having two paragraphs as a narrative unit. As the author has explained earlier on this method, a character and its edges could only be identified if another character appeared within the paragraph(s). Although a list of important character has been drawn up. If the author or translator of the novel has used one or multiple paragraph(s) in depicting one character without the occurrence of another character also occurred in that/those paragraph(s), the singled-out character will not be identified as a node along with its edges.

There is no absolute right or wrong pick for optimising the accuracy in interaction identification through paragraphs. For the one paragraph method, our algorithm loses out seven characters. For the second paragraph method, our algorithm potentially faces non-existence character co-occurrences. Let us take the higher number of nodes as the indicator on the accuracy in interaction identification, by applying the theory on paragraph as narrative unit on the method of having one whole chapter as a narrative unit. We see a total number of 311 nodes and 16419 edges identified. This means that the highest number of characters we can identify from our text is 311 and

the additional 10402 edges are non-existent as this is the worst consequence in setting our research scope to one scene per chapter.

After knowing the worst consequences and the best gains on each method, we have sufficient evidence to say the two-paragraphs method has the best deal in the compromising edges for nodes, as seven additional characters are included with the cost of some potential non-existent co-occurrences within the 783 additional edges. In which it is insignificant compared to the additional 10402 edges in the one chapter per scene method. In the following centrality analysis and content discussion, the results the author obtained from the two-paragraphs narrative unit method will be used mainly.

4.3 Centrality analysis

Centrality analysis is used to calculate centrality measures, which help quantify a character's importance based on his/her interactions with other characters. Centrality analysis often calculates the centrality measures of degree centrality, betweenness centrality and eigenvector centrality. Degree centrality calculates the number of links each character has, a simple way to define the importance of a character. Betweenness centrality shows how much a character helps connect other network characters that are not directly linked. It measures how many times a character is found within the shortest path that connects two other characters. Eigenvector centrality measures the importance of a character by the number of interactions they have with some other important characters. With eigenvector centrality, a character who interacts with a few important characters will score higher than a character who interacts with many minor characters. In short, degree centrality defines character importance by how many people a character knows. Betweenness centrality defines character importance by seeing which character could provide shortcuts to other

characters in networking. Eigenvector centrality defines character importance by seeing the quality of one's network.

As explained in the section of the case study review, Manolidis and Beveridge both used centrality analysis in their case study to identify the influential characters within the story. In addition to their methodology, for inspecting the power evolution between characters, they both split the text into different stages. Beveridge split the corpus by the novel's original parting (Beveridge, 2020). There are seven books in the whole series of *A Song of Ice and Fire*. In his project, a total of eight centrality analysis done with the last analysis focuses on the overall power structure within the whole series of seven books. On the other hand, Manolidis split the whole novel of *Romance of the Three Kingdoms* into four parts (Manolidis, 2019). There are 120 chapters within the novel. Each part consists of thirty chapters with an overall plot.

The author will implement the centrality analysis like Manolidis did. As explained in the text introduction, the novel *Water Margin* can be separated into three parts, the first part goes from chapter one to forty, the second part goes from chapter forty-one to chapter eighty, the third part goes from chapter eighty-one to one hundred.

5. Discussion

In this section, the author will discuss findings we observed from the outputs we obtained from the two-paragraphs interaction identification method and also the findings on the network with attribute data on character's qualitative information produced using Stanford Palladio. Four topics will be emphasised in our discussion. In the first topic, the author will discuss if our social network analysis can identify the minor characters who had influences on the important characters. The validation

process requires the influential minor character lists, which it is obtained through external resources. In the second topic, the author will discuss how the social network analysis illustrates the bandit heroes congregation process. Thirdly, a centrality analysis will be used to examine the importance of characters that appeared within the top three of our centrality measurements. In the last part of our discussion, the author will utilise the unique features of Stanford Palladio social network analysis and further explore the qualitative data on 36 bandits.

5.1 Important characters and their influential minor characters

For the exploration on this topic, the author decides to examine to what extent our social network analysis could identify the relationship between a few important characters with the minor characters who influenced those important characters. The author took a simple approach in determining important characters for this discussion. If the Wikipedia Water Margin character web page has listed the character individual's story, the author will consider that individual an important character. According to Wikipedia's *Water Margin* character list², there are 16 independent stories of important characters. Within each independent story, the web page has given a list of minor characters who had a significant influence on the story or the story's main character. To measure the accuracy of our social network analysis identifying the relationship between minor characters and the important character, the author will manually inspect the network and calculate the rate of successful recalls. The list of important

² Wikipedia, (2021) '*Wikipedia: List of Water Margin characters*', available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Water_Margin_characters

characters and their minor characters and the recall rates will be given in Table 1. In this section, the individual network from Chai Jin, Sagacious Lu and Wu Song.

Main character	Minor characters	Recall percentage
Chao Gai	Ho Tao, Ho Qing, Huang An	66.7%
Song Jiang	Poxi (Mistress Yan), Zhang Wenyuan, Shi Wenbin, Liu Gao, Liu Gao's Wife, Murong, Cai Dezhang, Huang Wenbin, Huang Wenyue	60%
Lu Junyi	Madam Jia, Li Gu	50%
Lin Chong	Marshal Gao, Lin Chong's wife, Jin er, Fu an, Prefect Teng, Sun Ding, Dong Chao, Xue Ba, Instructor Hong, Wang Lun	90%
Chai Jin	Gao Lian, Yin Tianxi, Yu Zhi, Wen Wenbao, Xue Yuanhui	40%
Sagacious Lu	Jade Lotus, Butcher Zheng, Squire Zhao, Master Zheng, Squire Liu, Cui, Second Son Qiu, Lucid Teacher, Zhang the Third, Li the Fourth, Deng Long	54.5%
Wu Song	Wu the Elder, Pan Jinlian (Golden Lotus), Ximen, Mistress Wang, Coroner Ho, Yun Ge, General Zhang, Instructor Zhang, Jiang the gate guard giant, Wang the priest	64%
Dong Ping	Cheng Wanli	100%
Yang Zhi	Niu Er, Governor Liang, Zhou Jin, Li Cheng, Wen Da	80%
Li Kui	Li Da, Li Kui's mother, Li Gui, Li Gui's wife, Squire	85.7%

	Cao, Luo the Sage, Han Bolong	
Shi Jin	Wang Jin, Wang Sheng, Squire Shi, Wang the Fourth, Li Ji, Prefect Ho, Wang Yi, Shuilan	87.5%
Lei Heng	Bai Yuqiao, Bai Xiuying	100%
Li Jun	Fei Bao, Ni Yun, Pu Qing, Di Cheng	100%
Zhang Shun	Zhang Wang, Sun Wu, Clever Pet	66.7%
Yang Xiong	Clever Cloud, Pei Ruhai, Ying Er	66.7%
Xie Zhen, Xie Bao	Squire Mao	100%

Table 1. Minor characters in the important characters' stories

Chai Jin's social network:

(Figure 1. A segment of Chai Jin's social network)

From the Wikipedia *Water Margin* character lists, we are informed that in the story of Chai Jin, five minor characters caused the social degradation of Chai Jin from an influential bureaucratic family member to a fugitive on the run. As stated in Table 1, from Chai Jin's social network, only two out of five of those minor characters are

connected to Chai Jin, which constitutes 40% of the characters' recall rate. To further study this low recall rate, the author believes it is vital to reinforce the social network with the original story.

These two connected minor characters, Yin Tianxi and Gao Lian are relatives. The latter has the support from his cousin Gao Qiu, the primary antagonist of the *Water Margin*. Gao Qiu is a corrupt governor blindly favoured by the emperor. With the powerful connection Gao Qiu has, Gao Lian took this advantage and scheme to take over Chai's manor by force with his relative, Yin Tianxi. The physical bullying from Yin to Chai has disturbed Li Kui greatly. It leads to the consequential death of Yin by Li's violence. Gao Lian gave Chai a death sentence with reprieve. The direct relationship between Gao Lian, Yi Tianxi and Chai Jin is straightforward. However, the rest of the three characters showed no direct relation with Chai Jin. Yu Zhi, Wen Wenbao and Xue Yuanhui are the military officials serving under Gao Lian, and they have been given the order to track down Chai the fugitive. In our network, we could only identify Yu Zhi and Xue Yuanhui and leaving Wen Wenbao undetected. These three minor characters are essential in Chai Jin's story because they represent the constant intangible danger behind Chai. It leaves Chai the only option to join the Liangshan Marsh and fight against the corrupted government. In the later part of the book, Yu Zhi, Wen Wenbao and Xue Yuanhai are killed by Lin Chong, Qin Ming and Hua Rong respectively. Our network successfully identified the co-occurrence between Yu Zhi and Lin Chong, Xue Yuanhai and Hua Rong.

The author's deduction for the low characters' recall rate for Chai's story is that those three characters only imposed threat to Chai Jin, but they never co-occurred or interacted with one another with their full names. For instance, when Chai's story is told from the Gao Lian's perspective, the threat that could expose Gao's wrongdoing

is Chai. When Gao stated his intention to his three military servants, Gao could refer Chai as 'him', and it would make sense to those three servants or to us, the readers. Therefore, there is a possibility the Chai co-occurred with those three military servants. Chai was mentioned in the conversation between Gao and servants, but not on a full-name basis. This could explain why the detection failed.

Sagacious Lu's social network:

The network of Sagacious Lu is another interesting subject to study. From the Wikipedia character list, we acknowledge that eleven minor characters played an important role in the story of Sagacious Lu. After the author's manual inspection, only six out of those eleven characters are shown to have a connection with Sagacious Lu, which constitutes low characters recall precision of 54.5%. Can Lu's story be able to explain the low recall rate?

Before discussing Sagacious Lu's story, readers must know the original name of Sagacious Lu is Lu Da. Sagacious Lu is his Dharma name given after his encounter with Lucid Teacher, as illustrated on the teacher's network. He used the name Lu Da committed the accidental killing on Butcher Zheng (Master Zheng) after hearing the unfortunes Zheng inflicted on Jade Lotus' family. With the help of Squire Zhao and Jade's family, Lu fled town and sought asylum in a Buddhist Temple, where he met the Lucid Teacher and was given the Dharma name Sagacious.

interesting to see Zhang the Li constructed an isolated network of themselves, but it is apparent that Zhang, Li and Sagacious Lu have connections between them. The author examined the translation text to explain the reason behind this phenomenon. It has been found that Zhang the third and Li the Fourth have been abbreviated to Zhang and Li within the context. According to Labatut and Bost, there are three ways text presents a character. Take the character Sherlock Holmes as an example, to address character in proper noun, the text should write 'Sherlock Holmes'; in pronoun, the text should write 'he'; in anaphoric noun, the text should write 'the Consultant Detectives' (Labatut & Bost, 2020, p7). If to address this phenomenon with Labatut and Bost's theory, the name abbreviation of Zhang and Li are anaphoric nouns, which it pre-requires a context to define the person, just like how Chai became an anaphoric noun in Gao Lian's conversation with the officials.

Cui and Second Son Qiu are two bandits who almost killed Sagacious for his valuables, but with Shi Jin's help, Sagacious and Shi killed those two bandits. The author has noticed that Cui and Qiu showed connection only to Shi Jin, but not Sagacious Lu. This phenomenon raised an interesting point to discuss. Before the Shi Jin's reinforcement, during the combat fought between Cui, Qiu and Sagacious Lu, Cui and Qiu used their aliases, Living Iron Buddha and Sky Flying Yaksha. As the examples have shown, anaphoric nouns can abbreviate the original character name, which can also refer to characters' aliases. Both of their full names are only revealed after the Shi's reinforcement, which was the only way character identification model could identify.

(Figure 3. The isolated network of Zhang the Third and Li the Fourth)

Wu Song's social Network:

(Figure 4. The social network of Wu Song)

We have been informed that eleven minor characters that play their important role in Wu Song's story from Wikipedia character list. After inspection, only seven out of eleven of those minor characters are connected to Wu Song on our social network. It constitutes the characters recall rates of 64%. In this section, the author will discuss the character cluster around Wu Song.

The cluster of characters around Wu Song hinted that there is a story between those minor characters and Wu Song. The story began with Wu Song's brother, Wu the Elder tipped by a street informant Yun Ge, that Wu the Elder's wife, Golden Lotus has been committing adultery with Ximen. The adulterers Golden Lotus, Ximen and the matchmaker Mistress Wang, realised the scandal has been exposed to Wu the Elder, and soon will be exposed to his brother Wu Song. The latter will bring physical harm to both adulterers and the matchmaker. The adultery gang of three decided to poison Wu the Elder and state he died naturally. Wu Song has been informed the truth behind his brother's death, and he got his brother's skeletal evident from Coroner Ho. Wu Song avenged his brother's death by murdering both adulterers.

From Wu Song's social network, we see the two other important minor characters, the street informant Yun Ge and Coroner Ho did not appear on the network. Two typo mistakes are found on the project's JSON character file when the author troubleshoots this issue. Due to the time limits, the author will not be able to have this issue fix immediately. The author predicts these two characters will appear around the cluster of characters when this issue is solved.

(Figure 6. Bandit Heroes' social network Phase 2)

(Figure 7. Bandit Heroes' social network Phase 3)

Looking at these three phases of the social network from an overall perspective, the author can see a strong sense of congregation between these heroes. From phase 1 of the social network, it is apparent that the nodes are generally dispersed, and there are many communities that are not too well interconnected with one another. According to Gephi's modularity report on this social network, five communities are detected within this network. The main character Song Jiang is the only bandit hero that has connections with all other communities. This could explain the reason why Song Jiang was voted as the optimal leader that could rally up the other like-minded bandit heroes.

From phase 2 of the network, five communities are also detected. However, unlike phase 1, a total number of 105 nodes are identified within this network, and the characters' network looks less dispersed than the former phase of the network. As the nodes have suggested, almost all bandit heroes have joined the Liangshan Marsh. Nevertheless, the important message in this phase is not about heroes meeting new heroes. The important message for this network is in deciding the ideology that could unify every hero within the Marsh. Song Jiang was the leading advocate to call for amnesty from the imperial court. Chao Gai (the former Marsh leader but excluded from the 108 heroes list) was the principal advocate to rebel against the imperial court. Song and Chao both were fighting for the same cause, which is to fight for social injustice that corrupted governors inflicted. However, Song believes the fate of the marsh should be legal and approved by the imperial court and the corrupted officials, meanwhile Chao believes the fate of the Marsh should only rebel the imperial court, fight the lesser wrongdoing with a stronger wrongdoing, as long as the *Jianghu* moral codes approve it. It has been argued that the Marsh decide to follow Song's lead of

amnesty is because the primary opposition advocate Chao died before the decision could be made. His ideology did not prevail any further. Song won the vote by his popularity and the help from his strategist Wu Yong, who has direct connections with the minorities within the 108 heroes.

From phase 3 of the network, the author could see there are fewer communities, and heroes have a more balance frequency of interactions with one another. The Marsh is congregated under Song Jiang's lead, and amnesty has been approved by the imperial court. In the novel's third part, the imperial court dispatched the Liangshan Marsh to secure frontier and eliminate Fang La, the religious subjugator. The balance number of interactions signify that the majority of members in the Marsh were on the same mission. When we look at the outliers with small nodes in the map, they either died early in the war or did not attend the war. This explains why they are the outliers of this social network.

5.3 Centrality Analysis

In this part of the discussion, the author will examine the social position of some of the characters who made the top in different centrality measurements. In Manolidis' centrality analysis report on the novel *Three Kingdoms*, he used centrality measurement of degree centrality, betweenness centrality and Eigenvector centrality in his centrality analysis to identify the warlords, their generals and strategists within different communities (countries) (Manolidis, 2019). For *Water Margin*, the centrality analysis below could identify the important bandit heroes and their role within the Liangshan Marsh. This centrality analysis will mainly focus on the characters' degree centrality, weighted degrees, betweenness centrality and eigenvector centrality.

In phase1, it is apparent that Song Jiang is the central character within the first part of the story as he ranked first in all centrality measures. These statistics indicate to readers that Song Jiang is the protagonist of the story. Especially if readers take a closer look at Song Jiang's weighted degree, he has the highest weighted degree of 495, which is almost twice as much as the second-highest in this table. This signifies that the name 'Song Jiang' occurred many times and co-occurred many times with other characters.

The second top, Hua Rong ranked second in degree, weighted degree and betweenness. Hua Rong was an old friend of Song Jiang. Hua played a vital role in the first part of the story as he provided asylum to Song Jiang when Song was wanted for killing his concubine. From Hua's rank in the betweenness centrality, it is arguable that apart from Song Jiang, Hua Rong is another ideal candidate for being the 'middleman'. As figure 9 illustrated, Hua knows almost everyone in the three significant communities, and he knows at least one person from the two small communities. If Hua is asked to connect one person to an unknown person in a small community, his strong bond with Song Jiang could help him to any two people, as Song Jiang knows almost everyone.

The second top of eigenvector centrality is Liu Tang. Does it mean Liu Tang knows the most influential people? The best way to examine this is to have Liu Tang's social network compared to Du Qian's network, the third rank in the eigenvector centrality. From the comparison, the author has found that Du Qian has four less important characters connected than Liu Tang. Liu is also ranked third in degree and weighted degree. The frequent occurrence of Liu signifies that he is likely to have more frequent interactions with other characters. From the story, Liu was the most trusted fellow of Chao Gai, and he ran numerous operations with other bandit heroes without Song

Jiang. As Chao is not included in the 108 bandit heroes, Liu Tang became the bandit hero representative who opposes Song Jiang's call for amnesty. In other words, Liu Tang is Chao Gai's lobbyist. In order to persuade others to follow Chao, Liu needs to maintain connections with different decision-makers in the Marsh.

(Figure 8. Centrality analysis of the Bandit Heroes' social network Phase 1)

(Figure 9. Hua Rong's social network)

(Figure 10. Social network of Liu Tang and Du Qian)

(Figure 11. Centrality analysis of the Bandit Heroes' social network Phase 2)

As earlier part of this paper discussed, phase 2 of the story focuses on the heroes congregation and, most importantly, deciding whether the Marsh should follow Song Jiang to call for amnesty. In the second part of the novel, apart from Song Jiang, the protagonist, the author also emphasised depicting the story of Li Kui and Wu Yong. In the story, Li Kui was the sworn brother of Song Jiang. Wu Yong was the strategist of Song Jiang. Both characters played their essential roles in rallying the Marsh to stand behind Song Jiang's call for amnesty. In addition to these two characters, Lin Chong

surprisingly ranked second in betweenness centrality when his degree and weighted degree ranked 4 and 6 respectively. From these statistics, it is clear that Lin Chong was not mentioned that frequently in the text, but when Lin Chong's name is mentioned, it would get him to connect to many people and connect many times to Song Jiang, the most influential people in the story. Although many readers may believe Lin Chong would not vote for amnesty as the corrupted officials seriously bullied him in the past. However, Lin Chong has very similar characteristics as Song Jiang. Both of them have a strong sense of national loyalty even the country's legal system turned its back against them. Henceforth, the centrality analysis in phase 2 has successfully identified the critical amnesty advocates.

In phase 3 of the story, the character Lu Junyi climbed up to the top of the centrality analysis table. Many readers argue that Lu Junyi is ranked second in the Liangshan Marsh because his characteristics are completely opposite to Song Jiang, the first man of the Liangshan Marsh. Song Jiang is a typical strategist as he was an insidious man born from a bureaucratic family, he was not the material for martial arts, but he was good at governing. On the other hand, Lu Junyi is a typical landlord as he was a naïve man born from a wealthy family. He was not the material for governing but the material for military work. In the last part of the story when Gao Qiu the corrupted governor wanted to eliminate the whole Liangshan Marsh. He started his assassination from the top rank in the Marsh. So, Gao poisoned Song Jiang and Lu Junyi, two of the most powerful bandit heroes in the Marsh. The author believes Lu Junyi is more frequently mentioned in phase 3 than in phase 2 because, in the phase 3 of the story, the novel emphasises how Lu Junyi commands in the warzone.

As the analysis has shown, the characters who made top ranks in Marsh often strongly bond with the central leader Song Jiang. The bandit heroes' characteristics, idealistic

beliefs, talents, and occupations can significantly impact how central they are positioned within the social network. However, one should not mistake it as a natural outcome of society and circumstances. Ultimately, *Water Margin* is a fictional world, and the author(s) of the novel could dictate which characters should appear more frequently and how much they should weight within the community. It has been said that before phase 3 begins, the novel emphasises depicting social issues and ancient Chinese politics. As the phase 3 begins, the novel gradually transits into a warfare story, and it focuses less on politics. Readers have found the phase 3 of the story was written similarly to how *Romance of the Three Kingdoms* describes the battlefield. Henceforth, readers deduced that the third part of the *Water Margin* was co-written by Luo Guanzhong, the author of the *Three Kingdoms*. Luo Guanzhong was good at portraying war heroes and battle. The author of this paper believes the high occurrence of Lu Junyi was because Luo Guanzhong participated in the writing of *Water Margin*.

(Figure 12. Centrality analysis of the Bandit Heroes' social network Phase 3)

5.4 Stanford Palladio network analysis of characters' qualitative data

In Moretti's research and Isasi's case study, they explored the possibilities in visualising the qualitative information of characters in social network analysis. For this project, the author explores the possibilities and limitations of illustrating character's attributes through the visualisation of the geospatial network. To accomplish this task, the author has prepared two CSV files. One of them indicates the place of birth, place of death, characters' endings, original occupations, and their profile with URL links attached. The other CSV document has the coordinates information on every location mentioned in the main CSV file. Due to the limitation of time, the author has only prepared information on thirty-six bandit heroes.

As illustrated from Figure 13, it is apparent that many heroes come from the central region of China. The city of Yuncheng is the place where many heroes were originally from. There are 5 out of 36 characters are this city. They are Song Jiang, Zhu Tong, Lei Heng, Wu Yong and Guan Sheng. Their occupations have two things in common. First, they are all official workers, and second, they are all intellectual jobs. On the other hand, there are three heroes who came from the Shijie Village, and they are the three fisherman brothers, namely Ruan the Second, Fifth and Seventh. If we look closely to the Shijie Village on Figure 14 and 15, the location of Shijie village is situated right next to the Yellow River distributary, the Xiaoqing River. This location provides an optimal location for the three Ruan brothers to catch fish. Similar to Ruan, Li Jun's original occupation was a ferryman in Luzhou (present-day: Hefei). From Figure 16, we could see a lake called the Chao Lake next to Luzhou. This map proves the validity of Li Jun's occupation as the geolocation of the city create the demands for the ferryman.

(Figure 13. Birth places of the bandit heroes)

(Figure 14. The geolocation of Shijie Village)

(Figure 15. The Xiaoqing River next to the Shijie Village)

(Figure 16. The Chao Lake in Luzhou)

The other feature of the Stanford Palladio network is to clusters the similarities within the network. Figure 17 illustrates that only 10 out of 36 characters were able to secede from the post-war trauma. The rest of the characters either died in the war, poisoned by corrupted governors, or committed suicide. The likelihood of obtaining satisfactory outcomes after joining Liangshan Marsh is at 28%, which is relatively low. From Figure 18, the author has found that the bandit heroes who died in war tends to be recorded as 'unknown'. Meanwhile, the characters who died in Chuzhou represents the tragedies after Gao Qiu's poison on Song Jiang. Before Song Jiang died from the slow poison, he arranged the death for his most trusted fellow Li Kui. Song Jiang's strategist Wu Yong and his old friend Hua Rong committed suicide right before Song's grave.

There are many other combinations the datasets could visualise. However, this section concludes that Stanford Palladio has great potential in illustrating characters' qualitative information and the clusters of all these types of information. The geospatial visualisations of characters' information show us that the *Jianghu Shi Nai'an* depicts located in the central region of China. In addition to this finding, the geospatial visualisations could also validate the characters' occupations.

(Figure 17. The endings of 36 Bandit Heroes)

(Figure 18. Locations where 36 Bandit Heroes died)

6. Conclusion

In summary, the best way to conduct a social network analysis on *Water Margin* is to apply Elsner's two-paragraphs interaction identification method. This method recalls the most accurate characters co-occurrences for our text. By applying this methodology, our project has successfully identified the overall social network, characters' network, the evolution of social network and the central characters through the centrality analysis. With Stanford Palladio software, the dataset could identify qualitative information clusters and validate certain information with the software's unique geospatial visualisation feature. The different network analysis techniques this paper applied have certainly broadened the author's horizons. However, one must question if our social network analysis could present the complex nature of Chinese style relationship or the graces and hatred that circulate in the *Jianghu* the story depicts? In the author's opinion, the social network model we created could not quantify such complex nature of the information. If human instead of computers read the story, such complex information will be comprehended more thoroughly.

To conclude, understanding the complex relationship between characters is the fundamental task for the reader. Our network analysis could not provide a solution to this fundamental task, but instead, the different network analysis techniques we applied helped us understand a story from a non-narrative angle. Understanding a story from a non-narrative angle is the type of task the human brain could not easily accomplish, but computers can. This makes the fundamental difference between human brains and computers.

There are also other questions our social network analysis could hint at but not give a definitive answer. Take our finding on the centrality of Lu Junyi as an example. Our centrality analysis hints that depicting the military hero Lu is an indicator of intervention

from a different author. Yet it is not enough evidence to substantiate Luo Guanzhong's co-authorship with Shi Nai'an. To solve this problem, one must use an advanced Natural Language Processing model to identify the patterns in sentence structure. This is a common question being asked in the field of digital humanities, but this paper has no intention to address it.

7. Research limitations

Due to the time restriction, the author could not correct some of the typo mistakes that occurred in the JSON character list and redo all the visualisations. Additionally, time insufficiencies have also restricted the author from further exploring the Spacy Name Entity Recognition model. If the model was well trained, the model could identify each character's nouns, aliases, and pronouns within any given text. Additionally, during the observation, the author has found why the network analysis could only detect 107 out of 108 bandit heroes. From the character list, there are two Zhang Qing within the Marsh, one could write as 张清, and the other could be written as 张青. This is also a limitation faced by any character detection model that detects in English, as both Zhang Qing seem no difference between each other in English text. However, they are looking different in Chinese characters. One of the author's solutions is to implement advanced NLP techniques and train the NER model to identify which Zhang Qing is meant in what context.

8. Future research direction

As characters co-occurred from the social network we created, an undirected network is created between two characters. However, in reality, interactions in real life or

novels do not always have a reciprocal relationship. Within a non-reciprocal relationship, one person could hold a more substantial power than the other person. In order to quantify such complexity of relationship, the author suggests using sentiment analysis to identify to what extent the text was positive or negative. With the combination of sentiment analysis and NLP, one can identify which character is the subject and which character is the object. Hence, we could quantify the subject's feeling to the object. Although this method is still not enough to represent the complex nature of the Chinese style or *Jianghu* relationship, it is undeniable that it is a big step forward to solve the impossible.

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